

was saponified and extracted with petroleum ether (40°-60°) : ether (50 : 50) mixture, then fractionated over a 3% deactivated alumina column.

The petroleum ether (40°-60°) : benzene (1 : 3) eluate yielded a compound which on crystallisation from methanol gave a m.p. 128°. Further its identity was established through chromatography over silica gel, reversed phase and argentation T.L.C. The spectral data of the compound was compared with the data reported in the literature⁵ for $\Delta^{5,2,5}$ -stigmastadien-3 β -ol and found to be identical with it. Elemental analysis gave the formula C₂₉H₄₈O.

The benzene : ether (3 : 1) eluate yielded another compound which on crystallisation from absolute ethanol gave a m.p. 288° (acetyl derivative m.p. 185°). The mass spectrum of this compound yielded a molecular weight of 442, showed a major fragmentation at m/e 234 and a strong peak m/e 411 (m-31). The I. R., NMR., data of the compound and its acetyl derivative were found to be identical with that of erythrodiol^{6,7}. Elemental analysis of the compound gave a formula C₃₀H₅₀O₂ and its acetyl derivative as C₃₄H₅₄O₄.

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Kinetics of the Reaction of cis-Dichlorodiammine Platinum (II) with Oxalate Ion in Aqueous Solution.

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CHEMICALS : cis-Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂ was prepared by the method described by Keller¹ and Kauffman and Cowan². (Found : Pt, 65.34 ; Cl, 24.03 per cent. Calc. for cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ : Pt, 65.02 ; Cl, 23.62 per cent). Aqueous complex solution exhibited an absorption maximum at 300 nm and a minimum at

247 nm in agreement with the observations of Teggini, McCann and Smith³ and Reishus and Martin⁴. The product of the reaction, cis-Diammino (oxalate) Platinum (II), was synthesized under the same conditions that were used in the kinetic runs. (Found : Pt, 61.21 ; C₂O₄, 27.33 per cent. Calc. for cis-Pt (NH₃)₂ C₂O₄ : Pt, 61.49 ; C₂O₄ ; 27.74 per cent). The compound was insoluble in water and hence the absorption spectrum could not be obtained.

Kinetics : The kinetic study involved the potentiometric method. The reaction was initiated by adding ammonium oxalate solution to a thermostated solution of the cis-Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂ kept at the desired temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The progress of the reaction between cis-Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂ and ammonium oxalate was followed by measuring the increase in chloride ion concentration with the help of a Ag/AgCl electrode dipped into the reaction mixture using saturated calomel electrode as a reference one. The rates generally exhibited good reproducibility. In most of the experiments the progress of the reactions was followed until the reagent concentrations had decreased to about half their original values.

In a different set of experiments different excess concentrations of oxalate ion compared to the complex ion concentrations were used. It was found that the rate is independent of oxalate ion concentration and a first-order rate law, as defined by equation (1), was thus established,

$$\text{rate} = k[\text{cis-Pt (NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The experiments were conducted in solutions having different desired pH values adjusted by the addition of perchloric acid or sodium hydroxide solutions. The effect of temperature on the reactions have been studied at pH 6.2 and the values of ΔH^* , the enthalpy of activation and ΔS^* , the entropy of activation have been calculated from the usual Eyring equation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the first-order rate constants for various reaction conditions. The results indicated that $\Delta H^* = 18.2$ KCal/mole and $\Delta S^* = -18.9$ e.u. for the reaction.

TABLE 1—FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION BETWEEN CIS-PT(NH₃)₂CL₂ AND AMMONIUMOXALATE UNDER VARIOUS CONDITIONS

10 ³ [cis-Pt(NH ₃) ₂ Cl ₂] M	10 ³ [oxalate] M	Temp. °C	pH	10 ⁵ k Sec ⁻¹
4.0	40.0	30	6.2	2.5
4.0	40	35	6.2	
4.0	80	35	6.2	
4.0	120	35	6.2	5.1
4.0	160	35	6.2	
4.0	40	40	6.2	9.0
4.0	80	45	6.2	13.0
4.0	80	50	6.2	22.6
4.0	80	35	3.2	4.3
4.0	80	35	8.4	4.6

The reaction rate for the substitution of cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ by oxalate is found to be almost pH independent throughout the pH range 3 to 9 indicating C₂O₄²⁻ and HC₂O₄⁻ have similar reactivities which agrees with the observations by Teggin, Lee, Baker and Smith⁵.

In four sets of experiments at 35° in which the initial molar concentration ratio of cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ and oxalate ranged from 1 : 10 to 1 : 40, values for the rate constants of 4.8-5.4 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹, av. 5.1 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ were obtained. The established values of the first-order rate constant k = 5.1 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 35°, the enthalpy of activation ΔH* = 18.2 KCal/mole and the entropy of activation ΔS* = -18.9 e.u. may be compared with the corresponding values reported for the first acid hydrolysis of this complex by Reishus and Martin⁴ (e. g., k = 7.6 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 35° ΔH* = 19.7 KCal/mole and ΔS* = -14.0 e.u.). But the value of k = 22.6 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 50° for the cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂-oxalate reaction is in rather poor agreement with the values of 39.0 × 10⁻⁵ sec⁻¹ at 50° for the same reaction reported by Teggin, Lee, Baker and Smith⁵. However, the value of ΔH* = 18.2 KCal/mole more or less agrees with the activation energy of 17.0 KCal/mole for this reaction reported by them.

It appears that the negative value of ΔS* is caused by electrostriction resulting from the formation of a singly charged three coordinated activated state [Pt(NH₃)₂Cl]⁺ formed by the first order dissociation of [Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂]⁰. The effect of increasing the ionic strength on the reaction rate is not however pronounced; this might be due to the formation of a neutral ion pair of the type [Pt(NH₃)₂Cl]⁺X⁻, (X⁻ = Cl⁻, HC₂O₄⁻) in the activated state.

The rate of oxalate entry in the complex cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ is being studied at present in order to see whether this rate is the same as or different from the chloride release rate. It is expected that this study will reveal the stoichiometric mechanism fully and yield clues as to the intimate mechanism.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Tantalum (V) by 8-Hydroxy-7-Iodoquinoline-5-Sulphonic acid And Stability Constant of the Complex.

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8-Hydroxy-7-Iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (Ferron) was used for the determination of tantalum(V) and stability constant of the Tantalum(V)-Ferron complex, by spectrophotometric studies. The effect of

diverse ions has been investigated. The method developed is rapid, sensitive and convenient since this complex is not required to be extracted by non-aqueous solvents.

Experimental

Beckman DU spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells of 1 cm. path length were used. The pH measurements were made with a pH meter (Toshniwal, India) having single electrode system. Tantalum pentoxide was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay and Ferron was a product of B.D.H. (A.R.).

Tantalum pentoxide was fused with potassium bisulphate to a clear melt. After cooling the melt was extracted with 25% solution of citric acid¹.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectrum : The complex shows maximum absorbance at 365 nm. Water was used as a reference.

Effect of pH : The effect of pH on the absorbance was studied. The maximum absorbance was noticed at pH 6.5. Hence in all experiments pH 6.5 was used. Dil. ammonia was used for varying the pH¹.

Calibration graph and stability : The Beer's law is obeyed within the concentration range of 100-500 ppm. The absorbance due to the colour system was found to remain constant for 2 days provided no evaporation took place.

Composition of the complex : To determine the molar composition of the complex formed, Job's method of continuous variation⁴ and the mole ratio method^{2,3,5} were employed. In Job's method the maximum in the curve clearly indicates the formation of Ta⁵⁺-Ferron complex in which the metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2. The mole ratio method was inconclusive but results obtained are in agreement with those obtained by Job's method.

The average value of stability constant, 'K' determined by these methods is K = 6.4465.

ESTIMATION OF TANTALUM(V)

S. No.	Ta ⁵⁺ taken mg.	Ta ⁵⁺ found mg.	Percentage Error
1.	1.900	1.885	-.78
2.	2.5	2.520	+.80
3.	3.1	3.090	-.32
4.	3.5	3.480	-.57
5.	4.5	4.478	-.48

Precision : The average of five determinations with 3.5 mg. of tantalum (V) is 3.480 mg. which varies between 3.44 mg. and 3.52 mg. with 95% confidence limit.

Interference : Nitrate, sulphate, thiocyanate, fluoride, tartarate and oxalate do not interfere. Chloride ion interferes above 100 ppm. Tungsten, titanium, calcium, ammonium do not interfere. Niobium and vanadium do not interfere if present upto 100 and 150 ppm respectively. Mo⁶⁺, Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺, Ba²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺ and Ni²⁺ interfere seriously.